

Supplemental Material

Identifying Conditions for Hydrogen Sector Coupling Amid Policy Shifts and Rising Electricity Demand

A. SUPPLEMENTAL FIGURES

Figure S1: Four different hydrogen demand projections used in this analysis

Figure S2: One week of normalized hourly demand data for the four demand scenarios used in this analysis.

Figure S3: Daily average capacity factor for all wind and solar resources in ERCOT over a full year. The same weather data is used for every investment period.

Figure S4: Heat map showing the annual energy consumption in 2033 for the nine load zones in SWITCH-ERCOT for (a) the 2023 load projection before large loads are considered and (b) the 2024 load projection that does include large loads.

B. POWER SYSTEM: SWITCH Model

SWITCH is a “modern platform for planning high-renewable power systems.” [2], and the program is typically used to study the long-term potential for renewable energy adoption in electric grids. The model ensures that at each hour electricity demand is met based on available generation sources. As electricity demand increases in the future, the model builds new power plants and increases transmission capacity wherever necessary. The build decisions are based on the lowest cost while maintaining prescribed levels of reliability. Both spatial load zones and temporal timescales are considered in SWITCH. Load zones are geographic areas in the region of study that consist of aggregate supply and demand in that region. Bulk transmission lines allow electricity to be shared between load zones. Timescales define various lengths of time. A timepoint defines where operational decisions are made, typically hourly. A timeseries is a chronological group of

timepoints, such as a week or a month. A period is a chronological group of time series that make up a year or more, so investment decisions can be made. Here we briefly summarize the core governing constraints and equations in SWITCH and SWITCH-ERCOT. Additional information on the model formulation is available in the SWITCH 2.0 documentation, found [here](#). The original SWITCH repository is found [here](#), while the custom version of SWITCH used in this analysis (SWITCH-ERCOT) is available here: https://github.com/RESET-Lab/SWITCH-ERCOT/tree/sector_coupling_2026

Objective function: SWITCH optimizes a modeled region to minimize the net present value of the total system cost over the time horizon of the model. For each investment period, all investment costs are annualized and converted into yearly fixed costs and summed together with fixed operational costs. The variable operational costs (fuel, maintenance, etc.) are multiplied by a weighting factor to scale those costs up to an entire year and then summed with the fixed costs to calculate the total system costs for that period. The costs for each period are multiplied by a discount factor to convert them into a net present value and then summed together to calculate the total system cost in a predefined reference year.

$$\min \sum_{p \in P} d_p \left\{ \sum_{c^f \in C^{fixed}} c_p^f + \sum_{t \in T_p} w_t^{year} \sum_{c^v \in C^{var}} c_t^v \right\}$$

Variable	Description
d_p	Discount factor. First converts the annual payments within the period to a lump payment made at the start of the period, then converts that single quantity into a net present value.
C^{fixed}	Set of all fixed costs in period P . This includes annualized CAPEX costs and fixed operational costs.
w_t^{year}	Weighting of each timepoint t in period P
C^{var}	Set of all variable costs at timepoint t . Includes fuel costs and other variable operational costs.

Investment constraints: In each investment period, SWITCH decides how much capacity to build for each generation or storage project for each load zone, as well as for each transmission line between load zones. While the model will tend to select generation options that result in the lowest-cost grid required to meet demand, these investment decisions are restricted by minimum and maximum build requirements. These limits may reflect capacity requirements from policy initiatives, expected builds from an interconnection queue, or may limit installations based on external factors not accounted for in the model, like land availability. For this particular analysis, each technology has a minimum capacity requirement in the 2025 period to reflect planned builds in ERCOT’s interconnection queue, but no additional capacity requirements are considered. Wind

and solar projects have their maximum capacities constrained by land availability in each load zone.

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{g,p}^G &= \sum_{p' \in \mathcal{P}_{g,p}^{\text{on}}} B_{g,p'}^G, & \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \cup \{p_0\} \\
B_{g,p}^G &= b_{g,p}^G, & \forall g \in \mathcal{G}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_g^G \\
K_{\ell,p}^L &= \sum_{p' \in \mathcal{P} \cup \{p_0\}: p' \leq p} B_{p',k}^L, & \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \\
B_{\ell,p}^L &= b_{\ell,p}^L, & \forall \ell \in \mathcal{L}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_\ell^L \\
0 \leq K_{g,p}^G &\leq \overline{k}_g^G, & \forall g \in \mathcal{G}^{\text{rc}}, p \in \mathcal{P}
\end{aligned}$$

Variable	Description
$B_{g,p}^G$	Decision variable for the amount of capacity of generator g built in period P , units of MW.
$b_{g,p}^G$	Predetermined amount of capacity of generator g built in period P , units of MW.
$K_{g,p}^G$	Total available capacity for generator g in period P . This is the sum of all the total installations that are still available in period P , meaning that capacity that would be retired based on the specified lifetime of the project is excluded. Units of MW.
\overline{k}_g^G	Upper limit for the amount of capacity that can be installed for a generator, units of MW.
$B_{\ell,p}^L$	Decision variable for the amount of capacity of transmission line l built in period P , units of MW.
$b_{\ell,p}^L$	Predetermined amount of capacity of transmission line l built in period P , units of MW.
$K_{\ell,p}^L$	Total available capacity for transmission line l in period P . Retirements are not considered for transmission lines. It is assumed that any new transmission lines will be reconstructed when they are set to retire. Units of MW.

$$\begin{aligned}
K_{h,p}^H &= \sum_{p' \in \mathcal{P}_{h,p}^{\text{on}}} B_{h,p'}^H, & \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \cup \{p_0\} \\
B_{h,p}^H &= b_{h,p}^H, & \forall h \in \mathcal{H}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_h^H \\
K_{s,p}^S &= \sum_{p' \in \mathcal{P} \cup \{p_0\}: p' \leq p} m_p B_{p',k}^S, & \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P} \\
B_{s,p}^S &= b_{s,p}^S, & \forall s \in \mathcal{S}, \forall p \in \mathcal{P}_s^S \\
0 \leq K_{h,p}^H &\leq \overline{k}_h^H, & \forall h \in \mathcal{H}^{\text{rc}}, p \in \mathcal{P}
\end{aligned}$$

Variable	Description
$B_{h,p}^H$	Decision variable for the amount of capacity of hydrogen facility h built in period P , units of kg/h.
$b_{h,p}^H$	Predetermined amount of capacity of hydrogen facility h built in period P , units of kg/h.
$K_{h,p}^H$	Total available capacity for hydrogen facility h in period P . This is the sum of all the total installations that are still available in period P , meaning that capacity that would be retired based on the specified lifetime of the project is excluded. Units of kg/h.
\bar{k}_h^H	Upper limit for the amount of capacity that can be installed for a hydrogen facility, units of kg/h.
$B_{s,p}^S$	Decision variable for the amount of capacity of transmission line l built in period P , units of kg/h.
$b_{s,p}^S$	Predetermined amount of capacity of pipeline s built in period P , units of kg/h.
$K_{s,p}^S$	Total available capacity for pipeline s in period P . Retirements are not considered for pipelines. It is assumed that any new pipelines will be reconstructed when they are set to retire. Built pipeline capacity is multiplied by its blending limit to get the available working capacity for hydrogen. Units of kg/h.
m_p	Blending limit for pipeline p , represented as a fraction of pipeline capacity that can be used to transport hydrogen safely.

Operations constraints: Generation, storage, and transmission decisions are made for every timepoint in the model. While SWITCH provides different constraints to represent different types of dispatch and commitment decisions, the “no commit” option is presented here as it is used in SWITCH-ERCOT. In this case, dispatch decisions are only limited by the available capacity in a period. Available capacity is derated by their planned and forced outage factors. Variable generation resources, like wind and solar, are also derated by their capacity factor at each timepoint. While not shown here, storage projects like batteries are subject to additional expressions and constraints to track their state of charge and limit their charging and discharging based on their available energy, total capacity, and roundtrip efficiency. All dispatch decisions are also governed by a power balance constraint, which requires that all inputs of energy into a load zone must be equal to the consumption and removal of energy to ensure that demand is being met at every timepoint.

$$\begin{aligned}
0 \leq P_{g,t} &\leq \eta_g K_{g,p(t)}^G, & \forall g \in \mathcal{G} - \mathcal{G}^R, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}_g^{\text{on}} \\
0 \leq P_{g,t} &\leq \eta_g \eta_{g,t} K_{g,p(t)}^G, & \forall g \in \mathcal{G}^R, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}_g^{\text{on}}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\sum_{p^i \in \mathcal{P}^{inject}} p_{z,t}^i = \sum_{p^w \in \mathcal{P}^{withdraw}} p_{z,t}^w, \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}$$

Variable	Description
$P_{g,p}$	Dispatch decision variable for generator g built in period P , units of MW.
η_g	Outage derating factor for generator g built in period P . Proportion of time a generator is expected to be available
$\eta_{g,t}$	Proportion of installed capacity that is the maximum output from a renewable project in timepoint t
p^{inject}	Set of all power injections to zone z at timepoint t . This could be generation from resources in the load zone, storage discharging, or incoming power on transmission lines.
$p^{withdraw}$	Set of all power withdrawals from zone z at timepoint t . This includes energy demand, storage charging, or outgoing power on transmission lines.

$$0 \leq D_{h,t} \leq K_{h,p(t)}^H, \quad \forall h \in H, \forall t \in T_g^{on}$$

$$\sum_{d^i \in \mathcal{D}^{inject}} d_{z,t}^i = \sum_{d^w \in \mathcal{D}^{withdraw}} d_{z,t}^w \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall t \in T$$

$$\sum_{h \in H_z} \frac{D_{h,t}}{\eta_h} \leq \sum_{g \in G_z^R} D_{g,t} \quad \forall z \in \mathcal{Z}, \forall t \in T$$

Variable	Description
$D_{h,t}$	Dispatch decision variable for hydrogen facility h at timepoint t , units of kg/h.
p^{inject}	Set of all hydrogen injections to zone z at timepoint t . This could be hydrogen production from resources in the load zone, storage withdrawal, or incoming hydrogen on pipelines.
$p^{withdraw}$	Set of all hydrogen withdrawals from zone z at timepoint t . This includes hydrogen demand, storage injections, or outgoing hydrogen on pipelines.
G_z^R	Set of all new renewable energy projects that are installed in zone z .
H_z	Set of all hydrogen production facilities that are built in zone z .
η_h	Efficiency of hydrogen production facilities, units of kg/MWh

Load zones

For this model, ERCOT is aggregated into nine regions. Eight of these regions align with the weather zones defined by ERCOT, which allows us to use historical data published by the ISO for those regions. An additional load zone is included to represent the panhandle. However, since

ERCOT does not publish load data for the Panhandle and the population in that region is so small, demand is assumed to be zero in the panhandle and the region is primarily used as an option for new land-based wind development.

Figure S5: Map of the nine load zones used in this analysis

References

- [1] “Long-Term Hourly Peak Demand and Energy Forecast Mid-Year Update,” Electric Reliability Council of Texas, July 2024. Accessed: Nov. 27, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://www.ercot.com/files/docs/2024/01/18/2024_LTLF_Report.docx
- [2] J. Johnston, R. Henriquez-Auba, B. Maluenda, and M. Fripp, “Switch 2.0: A modern platform for planning high-renewable power systems,” *SoftwareX*, vol. 10, p. 100251, July 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.softx.2019.100251.